

The Usefulness of Data in the Study of the Feminisation and Re-Masculinisation of Religion in Spain (1880-1930)

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ABSTRACT: The feminisation of religion is a category used for organizing the knowledge on sexual difference in modern imaginary. Concerning Spain at the turn of the twentieth century, the analysis of data on the participation of men and women in pious activities can serve to enrich the study of the feminisation and re-masculinisation of religion. First, it allows us to assess that the pious practices related to the most significant dates in the Catholic calendar was, regularly, similar for both sexes. Moreover, the use of data can test the hypothesis that sometimes there existed a notion of feminisation of religion even in a context where there was no substantial difference de facto between sexes concerning religious practice. This phenomenon could be explained by such a notion being imported from places where such a trend was indeed underway. I do not argue for a return to the ways and methods typical of social history in its heyday; what I strive for is to engage with the current lines of research on the feminisation and re-masculinisation of religion and carry out a nuanced analysis of the available data that would enrich or modify the prevailing interpretation of both phenomena.

KEYWORDS: Gender; Women; Sexual difference; Catholicism; Catholic Church; Religious Practice.

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Título traducido: La utilidad de los datos en el estudio de la feminización y remasculinización de la religión en España (1880-1930).

RESUMEN: La feminización de la religión es una categoría utilizada en el imaginario moderno para organizar el conocimiento sobre la diferencia sexual. En España, el análisis de los datos sobre la participación de los hombres y de las mujeres en las actividades piadosas a finales del siglo XIX y a comienzos del XX puede servir para enriquecer el estudio de la feminización y la re-masculinización de la religión. Por un lado, permite evaluar si la práctica piadosa relacionada con las fechas más importantes para la Iglesia católica era, por norma general, similar entre hombres y mujeres. Por otro lado, el uso de los datos posibilita poner a prueba la hipótesis de que, en ocasiones, en lugares donde no había una diferencia sustancial entre la práctica religiosa de hombres y de mujeres estaba arraigada la noción de que la religión era practicada más habitualmente por mujeres. Este fenómeno puede ser explicado por la posibilidad de que esta idea fuese importada desde lugares en los que sí existía un mayor compromiso religioso de las mujeres con la religión. Este artículo no propone regresar a los métodos típicos de la historia social; por el contrario, plantea conectar el análisis de los datos con las nuevas líneas de investigación sobre la feminización y la re-masculinización de la religión con el objetivo de enriquecer o modificar las interpretaciones predominantes sobre ambos fenómenos.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Género; Mujeres; Diferencia sexual; Catolicismo; Iglesia católica; Práctica religiosa.

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RELIGION IN MODERN ERA: THE FEMINISATION AND RE-MASCULINISATION HYPOTHESES

The analytical categories of feminisation and re-masculinisation of religion have been widely applied and discussed by historians dealing with the relationship between Christianity and gender.¹ Joan W. Scott has argued that religion is an important element in the identity of many women and men, either in the sense of adherence or distance/opposition. Therefore, the variety of links between sex and religion should be analysed as a specific part of the process of construction of the difference between the sexes (Scott, 2018, pp. 30-59).

Since the 1970s, the feminisation of religion thesis has become central, hegemonic in fact, in the religious history focusing on Christian women. The first historians who wrote about the feminisation of religion studied American Protestants in the nineteenth century. Its original formulations argued that during the nineteenth century, a similar or greater percentage of women continued to participate in pious practices as they had done in the past, while men began to distance themselves from the Christian Churches and the religion in general (Welter, 1974; Douglas, 1977). In the 1970s and 1980s, historians applied social theory and a quantitative methodology to ascertain with greater rigour whether women engaged in religious practice in greater numbers than men. The authors strove to quantify attendance to mass and peregrination to holy sites, the communion, and the active participation in religious congregations. Hardly any studies on religion from the perspective of women's history were published in this period concerning the case of Spain, so, obviously, no dialogue was established with the above-mentioned trends in transnational historiography.

In the 1990s, French historiography played a leading role in this area of research and, therefore, a great part of the works published focused on Catholicism. At least initially, this did not imply a change in the objectives that the researchers concerned with this issue set for themselves. Influenced by sociological studies on religion and by the above-mentioned research concerning the USA, several historians, such as Ralph Gibson (Gibson, 1989, pp. 180-190; 1993), carried out quantitative research on Sunday mass attendance and on receiving communion during Holy Week. The studies concluded that women fulfilled these religious duties with greater regularity than men in France as a whole, according to the available data.

However, already in that period, the feminisation of religion thesis was being nuanced and questioned. The historians argued that the fact women were more active in pious activities and the defence of the different Christian Churches did not necessarily mean a more solid religiousness when compared to men. The argument went as

follows: women might have had other motives for their involvement, such as a desire for social life, or the higher level of fulfillment of religious obligations could derive from a culture of habit rather than from taking the faith more seriously (McMillan, 1990, 1991; Ford, 1993, 2005; Langlois, 1997; Calissano, 2001; Machen, 2019). This explanation shows great similarities to the arguments of several Spanish Catholic activists during the nineteenth century (Torrabadella, 1872).

Furthermore, several authors have questioned the supposition that the dominant presence of women in religious activities was a new phenomenon in the nineteenth century. According to Ann Braude, referring to Protestant and Catholic churches in the USA, the difference stemmed from the fact that in the nineteenth century, a female majority at religious events began to worry Christian leaders and intellectuals. As men wielded greater power in politics and society, she argues, Christian leaders considered the situation detrimental to their interests. Braude argued that, in any case, this concern was not based on "demonstrable demographic or institutional shifts" (Braude, 1997, p. 87), but on "narrative fictions" (Braude, 1997, pp. 92-93).

These works set the bases for a discursive analysis of the feminisation of religion that has become a popular trend in historiography after the linguistic turn. This approach assumes that reality has no intrinsic meaning and is signified through the categories used to interpret it. It has had a major impact on the interpretations of the feminisation of religion. The authors who adopt this approach understand the feminisation of religion as a discursive category used to organise the knowledge on sexual difference in modern secular(ist) social imaginary. Therefore, they are not interested in understanding the phenomenon as a quantifiable reality (Blasco, 2005).

Recently, several publications have contributed to enriching the debate on the feminisation of religion by focusing on the redefinition of masculinity that took place in Catholic circles during the second part of the nineteenth century (Werner, 2011; Van Osselaer, 2013; Pasture et al., 2012; Van Osselaer and Pasture, 2014). The authors who have analysed the so-called re-masculinisation of religion have shown that decreasing participation of men in religious practices did not necessarily mean they were less religious, as they could express their commitment by other means. In fact, some have argued that pious men played a key role in making their religion present in the new spaces of sociability, such as political parties or the press. In these spaces controlled by men, the religious men could and would act in defence of God and of their faith.² This interpretation is, in fact, quite similar to the argument employed by Spanish Catholic activists in the first third of the twentieth century, for whom it was less important for a true Catholic man to fulfil formal religious obligations,

¹ Five important historiographical overviews are available on the feminisation and re-masculinisation of Catholicism in Spain: Salomón, 2000; Blasco, 2005, 2018; Mínguez, 2015; Camino, 2021. For a recent international assessment of these issues concerning Christianity: Werner, 2018.

² See, among others: Steinhoff, 2005, p. 227. Men did not distance themselves from charitable practices in countries such as Germany, either: Schneider, 2012. Neither did they in Spain; in 1900 men represented 44% of the membership of the Conferencia de San Vicente de Paul, one of the main charities of the laymen: Requena, 2002, p. 59.

than to “fight at home, on the streets, in the elections [...] : confess Christ in their home and public, loudly if needed: obtain the true freedom via vote; if voting is enough, and if not, a rifle against a rifle.”³

The process of re-masculinisation of Christianity religion during the late nineteenth and the early twentieth century, at the transnational level, sought to signify religious patterns as respectable features of a virile man, and thus make them perceive themselves as true men if they were pious and willing to defend their faith and the(ir) Church in public (Van Osselaer, 2017, pp. 171-172; Salomón, 2018; Romeo, 2018). The aim was to react to the pressure exercised by the liberal and secular discourses, that, in their fight for hegemony presented Christian men as less virile or effeminate and as incompatible with modern masculinity (Kirkley, 1996; Prestjan, 2011). Christian groups felt a great need to counter this discourse, a sense of urgency that can be attributed to the fact that post-Enlightenment gender discourse—that was becoming widespread during the nineteenth century—established a dichotomous relationship between men and women, and each sex had specific, often opposite, features and traits. In this discourse, femininity was linked to religion, feeling, and tradition, while masculinity was linked to secularism, reason, and progress. This discourse was at least partially interiorised by an important part of Christian men. At the same time, anti-clerical sectors insisted on a discursive feminisation of Catholic man, as part of their quest for hegemony.

These have been, during the last few decades, the main academic debates concerning the feminisation and re-masculinisation of the Christian religion, which lately have been systematized in some specific publications about the Spanish case (Blasco, 2005; Mínguez, 2015; Camino, 2021). These historiographic articles have stressed that, while there existed a process of a re-masculinisation of religion at the end of the nineteenth century and in the early twentieth century, this does not necessarily imply that Christianity had not been masculinised before. In the Modern Era, Christianity underwent several processes of feminisation and masculinisation, that followed different strategies adapted to each historical context and its demands. Thus, for instance, Spanish Catholic sectors made a great effort in the mid-nineteenth century to create a model of priestly masculinity adapted to a changing world that emerged from Spain’s revolutionary years from 1808 to 1843 (Romeo, 2021).

The Catholic concepts of womanhood and manhood should be carefully historicized for each case, taken into consideration that the ways the sexual difference between a Catholic man and a Catholic woman was built and understood varied greatly. Furthermore, values like charity and piety, considered as feminine in the secular discourses, were defined by Spanish Catholics as compatible with true masculinity as well as femininity. As Núñez-Bargueño has recently pointed out, we need to ponder whether the constant—and simultaneous—eff-

orts at masculinization and feminization of religion could have been, at the same time, a reaction to the ambiguous nature of gender and its complex relationship with the sacred (Núñez-Bargueño, 2019).

This article is a contribution to these general debates, based on the use of quantitative primary sources that have not yet been used to analyse the feminisation and re-masculinisation of religion in Spain. I do not intend to quantify the faith or beliefs of the Spaniards of that period, nor analyse how they experienced their spirituality. I aim at a new analytical approach to the study of the feminisation and re-masculinisation of Catholicism in Spain. The objective is not to refute the existing research, but rather to contribute to a more nuanced and precise analysis of the issue. Neither is this a call to include statistical data on religious practice in all the research concerning the feminisation and re-masculinisation of Catholicism in Spain, a demand impossible to satisfy in many cases, among other reasons because of the lack of such data in many regions. The following pages strive to show that, when analysing both phenomena, one needs to take into account the possibility that the period perceptions that many more men than women distanced themselves from religion and religious duties due to secularisation were not always based on reality. While in some regions the contemporaries could indeed base such perception on a direct observation, this was not always the case. It is impossible to ascertain whether the former or the latter was the case for each different region of Spain, but we need to take seriously the possibility of a lack of correspondence between the perception and the reality in an area.

THE NEED TO QUANTIFY THE RELIGIOUS PRACTICE OF SPANISH MEN AND WOMEN

During the period covered in this article, Spain was first a representative democracy and then a dictatorship. The Restoration (1875-1923) was a system that combined a rather powerful monarchy with a liberal model of state, in which the Catholic Church enjoyed great protection and privileges; in fact, Catholicism was Spain’s official religion, enshrined in the Constitution of 1876. The Catholic Church was granted control over marriage and education in Spain, and the government subsidized the salaries of Catholic clergy. However, this privileged treatment was not enough for the Catholic activists and Church representatives, who perceived themselves as a threatened and persecuted group within a society that was becoming more and more secular (Cueva, 2005, p. 49; Martínez Esteban, 2006). Many Catholics shared the notion that the Church faced a serious threat not only by the decrease in the number of believers but also by being questioned by people who did not share its dogmas. Spanish Catholics were concerned about the rise of anti-clericalism, particularly in the early twentieth century, when the anti-clericals acted against the Church and its power. Were these perceptions based on real trends? The data analysis shows important regional differences and shifting dynamics. For instance, “fulfilling Holy Week obligations” (*cumplimien-*

³ *La Atalaya*, 28 April 1903, p. 1.

to *pascual*, referring to a yearly obligation to confess and commune during the Holy Week) in the city of Logroño increased from 41% of the population in 1870 to 61.6% in 1911 (Sáez de Ocáriz, 1965). As for the region of Madrid between 1896 and 1927, the percentage of people who fulfilled their “Holy Week obligations” decreased slightly in the capital from 43.80% to 40%, while in the province as a whole increased from 49.07% to 55% (Cabezas de Herrera y Fernández, 1985, p. 124).

The Restoration was followed by a military dictatorship led by Miguel Primo de Rivera (1923-1930). Initially there existed a solid alliance between the officers and the clergy. At first, ecclesiastic and lay groups supported the new regime with great enthusiasm, considering it would be favorable to their project of re-christianisation of Spain and to counter the activities and efforts of the anti-clerical groups. However, the entente deteriorated as the years went by, as for the military establishment *the raison d’Etat* had priority over the Church interests and the Spanish nation over Catholicism (Quiroga, 2010). In this context, Catholic circles were not able to fully carry out their re-Catholicisation designs. In any case, one needs to keep in mind that, in the words of Mary Vincent, both in the Restoration and during the dictatorship of Miguel Primo de Rivera:

There was no sense in early twentieth-century Spain that religion was irrelevant [...]. On both left and right, religion occupied an imaginative space that made it omnipresent, even if not everyone adhere to it as a set of spiritual beliefs. Catholicism coalesced sharply as a *political* identity in Spain, a process that often had little direct connection with customary practice -whether baptizing children, ringing the angelus or celebrating *fiestas* in the pueblo- but which was, in turn, to politicize all of these (Vincent, 2017, pp. 124-125).

Taking into consideration this dynamic historical context, I consider it particularly pressing to complement the discursive analyses of the feminisation and re-masculinisation of religion in Spain with a thorough quantitative analysis (this article intends to contribute to this quest). While the historiography on France, for instance, has shed light on several aspects of both phenomena due to a multi-layered analysis of the mass attendance and the fulfilment of the “Holy Week obligations,” there are hardly any similar studies using quantitative data for these purposes for the case of Spain. Only a few works of research in religious history have assembled data for the period analysed here⁴. Nonetheless, these data were gathered to study the secularisation process and have not been analysed from a gender perspective, although there are some

⁴ However, in the Spanish case there is certain consensus about the fact that throughout the nineteenth century and the early twentieth century the proportion of nuns increased regarding the regular male clergy and practically their number tripled in absolute terms: Callahan, 2003, pp. 155-158 and 177-194; Minguez, 2014, p. 381; Ostolaza, 2018, pp. 53-55. At the time, there were also studies about quantitative data on this issue, so contemporaries not only had perceptions, but also certainties: Morote, 1904, p. 10.

exceptions (Marcos del Olmo, 2022). In this article, I use the data gathered by other authors and to this basis, I have added a series of unedited data on Holy Week duties, that can be found in different primary sources produced by the Church. These concern mainly the province of Tarragona. Therefore, I aim to study the variety of trends that existed in that specific region.

I do not argue for a return to the ways and methods typical of social history in its heyday; what I strive for is to engage with the current lines of research on the feminisation and re-masculinisation of religion and carry out a nuanced analysis of the available data that would enrich or modify the prevailing interpretation of both phenomena. In brief, my research strives to add a quantitative pillar to better support the purely discursive analyses. This methodological dialogue can bring about new hypotheses and prevent unjustified generalisations that, in my opinion, represent a major weakness of religious history when there is a lack of empirical data (Brown, 1992). The analysis of the numbers makes it possible to explore the “reality” of religious practices in each region and contrast it to the perceptions the contemporaries had concerning the religiosity of men and women, while at the same time acknowledging that these perceptions could end up impacting this practice. Moreover, it allows for a nuanced analysis of the strategies and intensity of the projects aimed at re-masculinising the religion in one place or another. The challenge faced by Catholic elites and activists when articulating and disseminating their ideas about Catholic men’s virility, was obviously not the same in a region where 10% of men and 85% of women fulfilled their religious duties, as in a region where 80% of men and 85% of women did so.

The researchers who wish to gather and analyse data on the religious practice of men and women in Spain face great difficulties, due to the territorial dispersion of these data as well as the fact that systematic data gathering took off later than in countries like France. This is a major obstacle to a complete study of religious practice in Spain during the last decades of the nineteenth and the first decades of the twentieth century, but partial studies are still possible and fruitful. The mass attendance and the commune (during the Holy Week, in particular) are the two most important religious practices to focus on, due to the data availability. In Spain, Holy Week duties were the most supervised religious practice and relevant statistics were produced, although they are dispersed in all kinds of archives and are often difficult to access. These two practices, Holy Week duties and Sunday mass assistance, were the easiest manifestations of religiosity to quantify for contemporary observers, although we must keep in mind that there are not the only ways to show piety publicly, and not necessarily the most important ones. However, when the contemporary observers assessed the religious commitment of Spanish men and women, they most probably focused precisely on these two displays of religiosity.

Even so, the figures on Sunday mass attendance and fulfilment of “Holy Week duties” must be analysed cautiously; they are not an exact reflection of religiosity in a

region. In fact, many parish priests in Spain pointed out that both indicators, particularly the Sunday mass attendance, were shaped by the fact that many men had to work on Sundays and holidays (Cabezas de Herrera y Fernández, 1985, pp. 121-122). For instance, in the small municipality of Argilaga in the Tarragona province, 100% of the inhabitants apparently fulfilled their “Holy Week duties” in the period 1879-1905. However, in the following years, the percentage of men fulfilling these duties decreased, while the figure for women stayed the same. This sexual dimorphism (*dimorphisme sexuel*) became strikingly obvious when 24 men and 2 women failed to fulfil their duties in 1916. The parish priest justified the data arguing that “the great part of the men, even the boys, do not attend the mass, they all work on holidays.”⁵ Moreover, the data were usually gathered by the parish priest and thus could have been manipulated in various ways for many different reasons and goals. As is the case of any primary source, the data that appear on the pages below are not entirely trustworthy.

THE FLUCTUATING RELIGIOUS COMMITMENT OF SPANISH MEN

When analysing statistical data on the Spanish men’s fulfilment of religious duties, we need to distinguish between several kinds of piety. Firstly, everyday piety. Secondly, piety linked to important dates of the Catholic calendar (Sunday mass attendance and the fulfilment of “Holy Week duties”). Lastly, piety displayed at exceptional events (such as the arrival of a mission to a village, processions, or demonstrations in defence of the Church).

Only a small percentage of Spanish men engaged in everyday religious practices during the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, both in comparison to women and in absolute numbers. Nonetheless, men’s piety regarding the outstanding dates of the Catholic calendar was higher than the percentage of Spanish men engaged in everyday religious displays. In fact, it is not exceptional to find clerics affirming—not always supporting their statement with reliable data—that more men than women participating in general communes, particularly during the Holy Week, for reasons that will be explained below.⁶

As for the displays of piety on exceptional occasions, the men participated in great numbers, particularly at the arrival of a mission to their town or village, and at the processions and demonstrations aimed at defending the Church. Sending missions to the municipalities was a common practice of Spanish bishops. These missions aimed at encouraging the fulfilment of religious duties, and they often succeeded in it. Thus, for instance, in Villa del Prado, in the province of Madrid, a great part of the

villagers went to confess when such a mission reached the town, though confessions were not so widespread in ordinary circumstances: “The confessions of adults reached one thousand: 423 men and 570 women; undoubtedly this was an extraordinary event.”⁷ All over Spain, it was actually quite typical in this period for men to attend to religious duties on exceptional occasions such as the arrival of a mission, even to attend in greater numbers than women did.⁸

Spanish men also made a public display of their Catholicism when participating in processions and demonstrations in the defence of the Church. The Spanish Catholic movement often clashed with both anticlerical circles and liberal governments during the first three decades of the twentieth century. In this context, some of the traditional public displays of religious fervour, such as processions and local festive pilgrimages (*romerías*) grew in number and acquired a combative dimension as part of a fight against secularisation and against the policies of liberal governments (Cueva, 2000; Suárez Cortina, 2014, p. 159). As the Catholics themselves considered these events as activities appropriate and suitable for men, due to them taking place in public, being sporadic, and having a clear political dimension, men tended to participate in greater numbers, equalling or surpassing women. The dynamic differed radically from the attendance to mass because even the committed Catholic men did not find it attractive enough. If the numbers in the Catholic press can be trusted, in 1904, for instance, a procession honouring the Immaculate that started in the Cathedral of Barcelona was attended by 8000 women and “men, at least three times more”⁹ and in 1910 about 500 men and roughly the same number of women attended a Via Crucis on a Holy Friday in a working-class neighbourhood in Barcelona¹⁰. Moreover, some of the Catholic demonstrations in the defence of the Church to which only men were invited to participate were an important success too, such as one in the city of Zamora that was attended by thousands of men and no women,¹¹ or another one in Murcia where 30000 men gathered.¹² One of the largest processions that took place

⁷ *Boletín eclesiástico de las diócesis de Madrid*. Madrid: Imprenta del asilo de huérfanos del Sagrado Corazón de Jesús, 1909, pp. 91-92.

⁸ *Boletín Eclesiástico del Obispado de Mondoñedo*, 30 June 1911, pp. 284-285; *Cartas edificantes de la asistencia de España. Año 1910*. Burgos: Tipografía ‘El Castellano’, 1911, pp. 100-101; *Cartas edificantes de la provincia de Aragón. Año 1911*. Barcelona: Librería e imprenta religiosa, 1912, p. 31, 224-225 and 254; *Cartas edificantes de la provincia de Castilla. Tomo I, número I*. Oña: Imprenta Privada del Colegio, 1912, p. 438; *Cartas edificantes de la provincia de Toledo de la Compañía de Jesús, 1913-1914 (tomo IV, número II)*. Madrid: Imprenta del asilo de huérfanos del Sagrado Corazón de Jesús, 1914, p. 146; *La Voz de Aragón*, 16 May 1929, p. 11.

⁹ *La Cruz*, 30 November 1904, p. 1.

¹⁰ *Correo Mariano*, 1 April 1910, p. 23.

¹¹ *Heraldo de Zamora*, 11 June 1910, p. 3.

¹² *Cartas edificantes de la provincia de Toledo de la Compañía de Jesús, 1913-1914 (tomo IV, número II)*. Madrid: Imprenta del asilo de huérfanos del Sagrado Corazón de Jesús, 1914, p. 75. While the gap was generally not so pronounced, we find other cases of Cath-

⁵ Arxiu Històric Arxidiocesà de Tarragona (AHAT), 7.21.1.2.5.1. Argilaga, l’. Parròquia de Sant Roc.

⁶ To mention several examples from different parts of Spain: *El Grano de Arena*, 12 March 1904, p. 3; *Boletín Oficial Eclesiástico del Obispado de Menorca*, 29 October 1904, p. 8; *Boletín del Clero del Obispado de León*, 30 March 1908, p. 26; *Boletín Oficial del Obispado de Orihuela*, 31 March 1926, p. 13.

in Spain at that time was organised in the framework of the 22nd International Eucharistic Congress, held in Madrid in 1911. This was an all-male procession, attended by over eighty thousand people (Núñez-Bargueño, 2021, pp. 559-561). Once again, Catholic men proved more than willing to attend an event of particular importance held in an urban area and display their faith and commitment in public.

During the late nineteenth and early twentieth century, women prevailed in societies that required membership and regular religious practice to participate in their activities. Thus, for example, the number of female members at all the centres of the Prayer Apostolate in the diocese of Osma, doubled or tripled that of male members, even though Osma was a region with a high percentage of Holy Week duties fulfilment among both men and women in that period.¹³ There was one exception, however: the Adoración Nocturna (Night Adoration), an exclusively male organisation that became a preferred space for Catholic men to profess and publicly display their devotion.¹⁴ Moreover, the members of this organisation proved to be more willing to participate in other acts of piety. Therefore, the Night Adoration—which reached approximately 100.000 members in the 1920s—was considered an example of a highly successful effort to mobilise Catholic men, and of the good health of Catholicism in Spain in general.¹⁵ As missionaries in the town of Cabañaquinta in Asturias argued, the fact that men and women participated in religious activities in similar numbers, it was thanks to the widespread membership of men in “the Night Adoration, and we already know that his blessed institution does a great good and has a remarkable impact on men.”¹⁶

In fact, it was quite common in Spain that more men than women attended night masses and communes. Often, more men came to Church at night than during the day, as it was precisely the night-time that made the attendance to pious acts more “masculine” for the Catholic men, in terms of both image and sociability.¹⁷ This trend became even more pronounced when night-time religious acts included a lecture on religion, labour legislation or politics,

olic demonstrations where men prevailed over women: *La Correspondencia de España*, 3 October 1910, p. 3.

¹³ *Boletín Eclesiástico del Obispado de Osma*, 15 January 1917, pp. 8-16.

¹⁴ *Boletín Eclesiástico del Obispado de Astorga*, 3 May 1899, p. 14; *Manual del adorador nocturno español*. Madrid: Consejo Supremo de la Adoración Nocturna Española, pp. 21-22.

¹⁵ *Diario de la Marina*, 4 December 1927, p. 42.

¹⁶ *Cartas edificantes de la provincia de Castilla. Tomo I, número I*. Oña: Imprenta Privada del Colegio, 1912, pp. 465-466. This assessment must be judged carefully, as other territories where the Adoración Nocturna did not operate also show extremely high levels of fulfilment of religious duties among men: *Región*, 13 April 1928, p. 13.

¹⁷ *Boletín Eclesiástico del Obispado de Astorga*, 3 June 1899, p. 18; *Cartas edificantes de la asistencia de España. Año 1910. Volumen I*. Burgos: Tipografía ‘El Castellano’, 1911, p. 171; *Cartas edificantes de la asistencia de España. Año 1910. Volumen II*. Burgos: Tipografía ‘El Castellano’, 1911, p. 70; *Boletín Oficial Eclesiástico del Obispado de Menorca*, 30 November 1926, p. 9.

and when they were announced as events exclusively for men.¹⁸

The cases listed show that, during the turn of the century, Spanish men expressed their commitment to the Catholic Church in different ways from those of Spanish women. The contemporary discourses on the feminisation of religion tended not to take this into account but rather focused on the frequency of mass attendance and communion. Consequently, both Catholics and anti-clericals considered an empirical reality that Spanish men were clearly less religious than Spanish women. Taking this into consideration, the strategy of religious re-masculinisation in Spain not only did strive to mobilise men who became hostile or indifferent towards Catholicism. It also had to focus on getting more committed Catholic men to engage in everyday piety and a public defence of the Church and religion. It was essential to shift the minds and change the practices of the men who still identified as Catholics, but perceived everyday religious practice as something feminine and not particularly rational, as they had interiorised the gender stereotypes linked to the religion of the liberal and anti-clerical discourses.

The explanation is, therefore, complex and includes several levels of analysis. Contemporary Spanish men were committed to Catholicism and popular religiosity but were less inclined to participate in the daily activities of the Catholic Church. In this sense, the analysis gets even more complex if we consider the existence of ecclesiastic religiousness, on the one hand, and popular religiosity, on the other. Both phenomena were not mutually exclusive but complemented each other in a complex and fragile balance. Popular religiosity tends to take on very diverse forms and requires the sanction of the Church authorities. In turn, the Church as an institution of power, deeply embedded in society, uses collective rituals to strengthen its cultural influence, social acknowledgement, and capacity of attraction among the population (Rina, 2015, pp. 181-182; 2021). Some religious practices such as mass attendance and Holy Week duties belong clearly within the Church religiosity. However, the other above-mentioned displays of religiousness such as pilgrimages or processions are harder to classify. To render the analysis even more complex, we also need to bear in mind that in specific contexts the requirements concerning certain religious practices could become laxer. Thus, for instance, in the 1930s, many heads of both male and female congregations established clear minimum standards of piety (Vincent, 2001, p. 286).

THE PERCEPTION NUANCED BY DATA: THE FULFILMENT OF “HOLY WEEK DUTIES” BY SPANISH MEN AND WOMEN

France represented a huge issue for the Spanish Catholics at the turn of the century. They considered the neighbour country as a place where the secularisation was

¹⁸ See, for instance: *La Atalaya*, 6 July 1893, p. 2; *El Diario de Murcia*, 30 March 1897, p. 2; *La Atalaya*, 11 March 1901, p. 2.

particularly strong and, linked to that, so was the feminisation of religion. According to the data that Ralph Gibson provides for the *fin-de-siècle*, there was indeed a pronounced sexual dimorphism concerning the fulfilment of “Holy Week duties.” In fact, in most dioceses, the number of women fulfilling these duties doubled, tripled, or even quadrupled that of men (Gibson, 1993, pp. 91-93).

These data were truly alarming for the interests of the Catholic Church and information in this sense was widely circulated in Spain. The press often published data on the religiosity of French men and women though sometimes exaggerated the above-mentioned trends. Thus, for example, the Spanish press maintained that in Paris only 2.55% of people fulfilled their Holy Week duties, and that only 1% of men and 5% of women communed regularly.¹⁹ The dissemination of such figures, and the French Catholics’ visions on the (lack of) religiosity and the gender gap in pious practice in their country, was fuelled by the fact that many important Spanish Catholic activists were convinced that Spain was on the same path as France in religious matters.²⁰ These beliefs had an impact on the way Spanish Catholics interpreted the situation in their own country. Had the Spanish Catholics carried out autonomous and rigorous analyses of the data gathered in Spain, they would have clearly appreciated that sexual dimorphism was, by far, not so pronounced in Spain as it was in France. Furthermore, the differences between Spain and France can be explained, among other factors, by the political/institutional dynamics in each country. While in Spain the Catholic Church was protected and privileged by the state, in France, by 1905 there existed complete legislation regulating the separation between the state and the Church, the result of a process triggered by the French Revolution.

Nonetheless, the notion that religious practice was feminised had real impact and consequences in Spain—and in many other European countries—around the turn of the century (McLeod, 2000, pp. 124-136 and 216-247). This perception was understood and accepted as an unquestionable reality, and the idea that religiousness was a natural attribute of femininity had a strong impact on politics (Salomón, 2004; McMillan, 1981). Why did the contemporaries of different political ideologies and cultures accept such a notion that was a clear consequence of the discursive link between women and religion? To answer this question is a challenge to historians who should not merely accept the period analyses and assessments on this issue at face value.

Could Catholic activists and believers come to accept as reality the feminisation of religion if the data for their region did not show major differences between men and women concerning pious practice? The answer is decidedly yes. If they did not base their notion on the actual

observation of a religious gender gap in their own environment, we need to ponder on whether in these cases the concerns and worries about the feminisation of religion could be forged and shaped through the importation of the interpretations from regions and countries where this phenomenon did exist. Often, experience is understood as the basis on which people become aware of a situation (Scott, 1999 [1991]). The fact that some of the people who fully endorsed the notions linked to a discursive feminisation of religion could not appreciate a wide gender gap in religious practice in their environment, invites us to consider other interpretations.

This is precisely the reason why it is essential to confront the perceptions with the data. These are two different levels of analysis, but they are complementary and enrich one another. The aim is not to solve the classic issue of the compatibility between reality and discourse, but rather to identify and understand the different perceptions that existed in Spain concerning the feminisation of religion, Spain being a highly heterogeneous and diverse country. The idea that women were more religious than men was well-established in the period imaginary. However, as the imaginary grants meaning to specific realities, it is hard to visualize that it would work exactly the same way in places where a major gender gap did exist and in places where people could not observe such differences in male and female religious practice in their everyday lives.

In some Spanish regions, sexual dimorphism in the fulfilment of religious duties was very pronounced at the end of the nineteenth century, even in very different areas, and independently of the rural/urban or centre/periphery factors. We can appreciate it in the following examples. In Aytona, a village of the Lleida province in Catalonia, 13008 women communed in 1892 in contrast to only 1544 men, almost 10 times more.²¹ In the city of Logroño, the fulfilment of Holy Week duties was highly unbalanced in favour of women in the last decade of the nineteenth century (Table 1), which is the period for which statistical data are available.²² In these regions, the imaginary involving the greater religiosity of women could fully spread, as the contemporaries could transfer it without major difficulties to the analysis of their surroundings.

The assimilation of the discourse on the feminisation of religion might have not been so straightforward in regions where the fulfilment of Holy Week duties was overwhelming between both sexes, and the people could not confirm the notion by direct observation. For instance, in places like the Sena municipality of the Aragon’s province of Huesca in 1885-1889, Vadillo in the Castilian province of Soria in 1875-1914, and Albiol, Guialmons, Vespella de Gaià, Almoester, or Creixell of the Catalonian province of Tarragona, in 1880-1910, almost all men and women

¹⁹ *La Lectura Popular*, 1 June 1902, 2; *Boletín eclesiástico de las diócesis de Madrid*. Madrid: Imprenta del asilo de huérfanos del Sagrado Corazón de Jesús, 1909, p. 466.

²⁰ *El tradicionalista*, 20 January 1907, p. 1; *La Semana Católica de Salamanca*, 10 July 1897, p. 12; *La Crónica de Huesca*, 4 October 1892, pp. 11-12.

²¹ *Crónica del primer Congreso Eucarístico Nacional*. Valencia: Imprenta de Federico Domenech, 1894, p. 457.

²² The data for those parishes of the Logroño city where a larger statistical series is available confirm that this trend continued for the great part of the Restoration: Andrés-Gallego and Pazos, 1999, pp. 350-351. I present the data as they appear in the above-mentioned work.

TABLE 1. Share of men among the whole population that fulfilled their Easter duties (women and children) in Logroño.

Year	%
1892	19.20
1893	15.28
1894	19.80
1895	17.0
1896	13.66
1897	15.53
1898	21.60
1899	16.33
1900	22.33
1901	19.40
1902	29.33

Source: Sáez de Ocáriz, 1965.

fulfilled their Holy Week duties.²³ This was the case in otherwise very different regions of Spain and in places with distinct characteristics. The first five examples, for instance, are rather isolated small towns with low levels of economic development, but the last two were very close to major towns and their level of economic development was higher. Were these localities hermetically sealed from outside ideas, their inhabitants could not realistically acquire a notion that women tended to be more religious, as no significant gender gap was observable there.

The diocese of Zamora is a particularly interesting example to analyse, as we have data for 1894-1915 concerning an important number of people (the city of Zamora had approximately 17000 inhabitants at that time and the town of Toro 8000). In this period, more than 90% of the population fulfilled their Easter religious duties. In 1915, 88.4% of men and 94.4% of women fulfilled their Catholic duties, a high rate for both sexes. To explain the slightly higher percentage of women, some authors have mobilised the concept of the feminisation of religion, as did several parish priests during the historical period analysed (Hernández, 2016, pp. 780-787). Taking into consid-

eration the high percentage overall and the gap between sexes being so narrow, it is hard to believe that such a perception about feminisation of Catholicism could emerge in the Zamora diocese autonomously. In fact, the local Catholic press published hardly any stories that would refer to or complain about Zamora men being less religious than women. Quite to the contrary, I have found several articles mentioning greater religiosity of Spanish women in comparison to Spanish men in other regions, as if it were a phenomenon inexistent in Zamora.²⁴ Therefore, it is highly probable that the concern some of the local Catholic groups felt about a feminisation of Catholicism was imported from other regions of Spain, rather than based on observation. This hypothesis is supported by the fact that in the regions close to Zamora, such as Salamanca, the situation was actually similar to Zamora with a high percentage of men fulfilling their religious duties, as the women did, at least according to the data on special religious occasions.²⁵ It is hard to imagine that in these regions where men fulfilled their religious duties in great numbers, as did women, the notion of feminisation of religion emerged based on experience.

As these selected examples show, it is extremely difficult to generalise on this issue for Spain as a whole. It is even complicated to do so for a region. Not even a province was necessarily homogenous. To give a very clear example, in the province of Valencia, the villages of Enguera and Estubeny, only 8 km from each other, display wildly different numbers concerning Holy Week duties. In Enguera, in 1900 989 men of 1292 men fulfilled this duty, while of 1488 women 1176 did. Both are high numbers showing great commitment of both sexes to Holy Week duties. On the contrary, in Estubeny, in 1901 there was indeed a gap between the percentage of men and women fulfilling the Holy Week duties: 42 of 94 men did so, to 86 of 116 women²⁶. The two villages differed basically in their economic development: while the former was experiencing a boom due to wool manufacturing industries, the latter's economic activity consisted mostly of agriculture and cattle raising at the bare subsistence level. In this case, the village with a greater level of economic development was the one whose inhabitants displayed a greater level of fulfillment of religious duties and there was less difference between men and women in doing so. This contradicts the period theories arguing that industrialisation and economic development led to a loss of religiousness.

The case of Spain's capital, Madrid, is striking, as there existed several parallel and contradictory trends. For this very reason, the notion that the Catholic religion was feminised could not become a commonplace in a straightforward way, based on observation. When examining the data on the Holy Week duty fulfilment among men and women concerning the years 1922 and 1927, the two years

²³ Archivo Histórico Provincial de Huesca, ES/AHPHU-S-000046. Quinque libri de la Parroquia de Nuestra Señora de la Asunción de Sena; AHAT, 7.8.1.2.5.1. Albiol, I'. Parròquia de Sant Miquel; AHAT, 7.13.1.2.5.1. Almoester. Parròquia de Sant Miquel; AHAT, 7.69.1.2.5.1. Guialmons. Parròquia de la Mare de Déu del Roser; AHAT, 7.50.1.2.5.1. Creixell. Parròquia de Sant Jaume; AHAT, 7.193.1.2.5.1. Vespella de Gaià. Parròquia de Sant Miquel; Andrés-Gallego and Pazos, 1999, pp. 350-351. In locations such as Alfaro in the Rioja province, almost all men fulfilled their religious duty at general communes even in 1912: *Cartas edificantes de la provincia de Aragón. Año 1912. Número 1*. Barcelona: Librería Religiosa, 1913, p. 54, and the same occurred in Rocallaura, in the province of Lleida: *La Cruz*, 14 October 1915, p. 1.

²⁴ *Heraldo de Zamora*, 2 April 1918, p. 1.

²⁵ *Cartas edificantes de la provincia de Castilla. Tomo I, número 1*. Oña: Imprenta Privada del Colegio, 1912, pp. 377-378.

²⁶ Servicio diocesano de archivos parroquiales de Valencia, 2.2-19. Enguera: Visita Pastoral 1900; Servicio diocesano de archivos parroquiales de Valencia, 2.2-15. Estubeny: Visita Pastoral 1901.

for which the most precise data are available, we observe that in some areas of the Madrid province, outside of the capital, the percentage of those who fulfilled Holy Week duties among men increased, while it decreased in others. And a similar variety existed among women. Nonetheless, the eleven parishes of the city of Madrid for which we have complete data in the two above-mentioned years followed a different pattern: in ten of them, the fulfilment of religious duties among men fell, while only in 6 of them the same was true for women (Tables 2 and 3)²⁷.

As one may appreciate from Tables 2 and 3, the trends

TABLE 2. Percentage of men and women who fulfilled their Easter duties in areas of Madrid province.

Municipality	Men	Women
Algete (1922)	30	50
Algete (1927)	40	70
El Escorial (1922)	69	96
El Escorial (1927)	80	96
Getafe (1922)	50	65
Getafe (1927)	20	40
Lozoya (1922)	24	39
Lozoya (1927)	20	35
El Molar (1922)	20	43
El Molar (1927)	25	65
Torrelaguna (1922)	34	41
Torrelaguna (1927)	60	80

Source: Cabezas de Herrera y Fernández, 1985, p. 125.

varied greatly even within a relatively homogeneous area of one single city. The Madrid parishes selected for comparison are all found close to the Puerta del Sol, leaving aside parishes in -then- peripheral areas of the capital, such as the districts of Palacio, Universidad, Inclusa, Delicias, or Chamberí. The aim is to show that remarkable differences and varying trends can be observed concerning the fulfilment of Holy Week duties by men and women even in those parishes that shared almost all social characteristics. Unfortunately, the article can neither include a detailed analysis of these parishes nor compare them to working-class suburbs, though we may speculate that, in such cases, the differences would have been greater, considering the social, political, and cultural differences between the center and the periphery. This research does not aim at intra-local analyses of such dimensions. Research that would examine and compare the parishes in different areas of the same city would indeed be extremely useful and, hopefully, could make use of the theoretical and methodological framework outlined here.

The ideas concerning a greater religiousness of wom-

²⁷ The data in the figures are presented in the same way as in the work of research where they were published.

TABLE 3. Percentage of men and women who fulfilled their Easter duties in parishes of the city of Madrid.

Parish	Men	Women
Santa Bárbara (1922)	65	85
Santa Bárbara (1927)	30	80
Nuestra Señora del Buen Consejo (1922)	25	50
Nuestra Señora del Buen Consejo (1927)	15	80
Nuestra Señora del Carmen (1922)	98	98
Nuestra Señora del Carmen (1927)	60	80
Nuestra Señora Concepción (1922)	65	90
Nuestra Señora Concepción (1927)	15	40
Santa Cruz (1922)	50	80
Santa Cruz (1927)	15	40
San Jerónimo (1922)	95	98
San Jerónimo (1927)	90	95
San Miguel (1922)	15	40
San Miguel (1927)	10	40
Nuestra Señora del Pilar (1922)	10	50
Nuestra Señora del Pilar (1927)	35	70
El Salvador (1922)	16	40
El Salvador (1927)	5	15
Santiago (1922)	24	60
Santiago (1927)	15	70
San Sebastián (1922)	50	70
San Sebastián (1927)	45	70

Source: Cabezas de Herrera y Fernández, 1985, p. 125.

en could not have had exactly the same effects and implications in each of the areas of the Madrid province. The situation differed from place to place; therefore, the Catholics of Madrid would have necessarily differed in their analysis of the statu quo, had they based their opinions on their experience in their place of residence. In fact, however, they tended to share the assessment about a growing de-Catholicisation of men in Madrid. This concern existed even in places where empirical evidence and direct observation could, in fact, be a basis for moderate optimism in Catholic circles, as the fulfilment of Holy Week duties among men was on the rise. This clearly demonstrates that reality was given a meaning which was defined through an acritical interiorisation of the discourse of feminisation of religion, rather than through personal experiences of such a phenomenon. This was sometimes noted by those contemporaries who tried to promote another take on the statu quo, in which men did fulfil religious duties. For example, a contributor to the Catholic newspaper *La Cruz* demanded that the press should cease to project the trends concerning men's fulfilment of religious duties in the capital to Madrid's hinterland: "We have to pay attention to this in order not to be unfair [...]. It will be enough for

my purpose to say that I have travelled to more than 400 villages and in none of them I have found half a dozen of men who would have stopped attending the sacred sacrifice of the mass on holy days, and I say the same about the Holy Week duties.”²⁸

While the data concerning Madrid make it possible to map very specific local situations and trends, the analysis of the parishes of the Tarragona province allows us to explore phenomena that have received little attention in Spanish historiography. My aim is not to compare the data from Madrid and those from Tarragona, the two regions being very different even in geographic terms. Instead, I wish to showcase the different realities that coexisted in Spain in the period analysed. Even if, in the future, when more quantitative studies of religious feminisation in Spain are available, the examples I will outline in the following paragraphs prove to be exceptional, they would still be meaningful exceptions that could help us rethink this issue differently. In sum, I will present several cases in which it seems that the discourse concerning the lack of religiousness among men and greater piety of women had existed before it emerged in practice. Therefore, I have selected cases of areas where the discourse on the feminization of religion preceded such a phenomenon in practice and not the contrary²⁹. This is the main factor I have considered when choosing primary sources on specific regions and left aside others. In all these cases, after a long period in which the number of men and women fulfilling Holy Week duties remained relatively stable, a sharp descent took place among men at the turn of the twentieth century while women continued to participate in Catholic rites in numbers similar as or higher than before.

In the Alforja municipality, the fulfilment of Holy Week duties among both men and women remained constant around 80%. Nonetheless, the situation began to change since 1904 and the fulfilment among men decreased rapidly, to become more or less stable after a while and even increase again, while among women it increased fast and steadily throughout the same period (Table 4).³⁰

Similar tendencies can be observed in the rural municipalities of Rourell and Rauric. During the first decades of the Restoration, almost everyone fulfilled his or her Holy Week duties, but the number of men who failed to fulfil this duty started to increase in Rourell since the year 1890 and in Rauric since 1900, while almost all women continued to fulfil them³¹ (Tables 5 and 6).

²⁸ *La Cruz*, 20 October 1906, p. 1.

²⁹ I have selected the years when a change regarding the trends in the fulfilment of Holy Week duties can be appreciated.

³⁰ AHAT, 7.11.1.2.5.1. Alforja. Parròquia de Sant Miquel. Even in the period when men failed to fulfil their Holy Week duty in far greater number than women did, they still tended to show up for general communes in a number similar to that of women: *La Cruz*, 23 February 1906, p. 1.

³¹ AHAT, 7.146.1.2.5.1. El Rourell, Parròquia de Sant Pere; AHAT, 7.129.1.2.5.1. Rauric. Parròquia de Santa Fe. However, when in 1912 a mission arrived in the municipality of Rourell and a general commune was organised on this special occasion, men displayed greater commitment to the Church than usual: *Cartas edificantes de la provincia de Aragón. Año 1912. Número 1*. Barcelona: Librería

TABLE 4. Number of men and women who did not fulfill their Easter duties in Alforja.

Year	Men	Women
1904	103	82
1907	142	79
1911	138	36
1914	121	19

Source: Alforja. Parròquia de Sant Miquel, 7.11, AHAT.

There was no major demographic shift nor anything exceptional happened to explain this sudden lack of commitment among men in any of the above-mentioned municipalities. For that reason, the explanation should consider general, not particular dynamics. Still, I would like to stress that the small town of Rauric was just 5 km from Gualmons, which shared many of its features but where the fulfilment of the Holy Week duties among men and women was close to 100% in the same period. I consider that the most plausible hypothesis is that it was in these years when the inhabitants of these municipalities began to get acquainted with the notion that religious practice was something feminine, idea that had circulated in Spain for decades. Such assimilation of external notions pushed many men and women to adapt to these behavioural patterns, that is, to adjust to what was considered as normal or expected attitude towards religious practice for each sex nationwide. Therefore, it seems as if men ended up distancing themselves from everyday pious practices when this became considered less prestigious due to its association with femininity. The interiorisation of this belief did not occur in a vacuum. Its development and expansion were linked to the rise of anti-clericalism and the liberal, republican, and socialist political movements and parties. These movements tended to interpret religiosity and piety as features inherent to femininity and fueled the understanding of pious practices as hard to reconcile with modern masculinity, a notion many men ended up endorsing.

I shall stress that the capacity of these discourses to spread among the population and get interiorised was not directly proportional to political affiliation and sympathies in a specific region. The results of three elections that offer the most complete data on political adherence (of men—as only men could vote then) in these municipalities during the period analysed here clearly show that the changes in men’s commitment to religious duties took place autonomously, with no direct relation to political allegiances and dynamics. The two main monarchist parties of the Restoration period, the Liberals, and the Conservatives, prevailed in Alforja at the turn of the century, but the Republicans were also becoming important. It grew in importance to the extent that in the 1916 election, it was the main force in the area, followed by the two Res-

Religiosa, 1913, p. 40. Rourell’s population at that time oscillated around 400, while approximately 150 people lived in Rauric.

TABLE 5. Number of men and women who did not fulfill their Easter duties in Rourell.

Year	1890	1892	1894	1898	1902	1904	1911	1915	1925	1926	1927	1929	1931	1933
Men	1	6	8	5	0	2	10	11	21	14	20	16	16	42
Women	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2

Source: El Rourell. Parròquia de Sant Pere, 7.146, AHAT.

TABLE 6. Number of men and women who did not fulfill their Easter duties in Rauric.

Year	1901	1902	1903	1904	1905	1906	1907	1908	1909	1910	1911	1912	1913	1914	1915	1916
Men	10	13	10	19	19	23	14	14	24	17	21	20	22	23	23	23
Women	7	6	1	10	10	5	2	3	1	0	5	4	4	5	5	4

Source: Rauric. Parròquia de Santa Fe, 7.129, AHAT.

toration parties, the Catholic forces lagging far behind. Despite this major political shift, the number of men who abstained from fulfilling the Holy Week duties remained stable.

Rourell offers a very different picture. At the end of the nineteenth century, the two monarchist parties of the Restoration received similar support of voters as the different republican candidates, in a period when almost all men of the municipality fulfilled their Holy Week duties. In the following decades, conservative, Catholic and monarchist forces made important gains in votes, becoming hegemonic. Nonetheless, the electoral decline of republican and anti-clerical forces was parallel to a fall in the fulfilment of Holy Week duties among men. That is, the growing impact of the anti-clerical discourse that linked piety to femininity did not necessarily imply major success for anti-clerical parties, and vice versa³².

Let me conclude with Constantí, a municipality of the Tarragona province which shows a pattern different from all the examples we have discussed up to this point. Even if its exceptionality is confirmed in future quantitative studies concerning whole of Spain, this is another case that invites us to ponder the feminisation of Catholicism from new angles, in a different way from the great part of existing analyses. From 1893 to 1901, the period for which data are available, women of Constantí prevailed over men in abstaining from fulfilling Holy Week duties (Table 7).³³ This location, with less than 2500 inhabitants and ordinary demographic features considering the proportion of men and women in the population, is a proof of the existence of places where more men than women took part in religious practices. The behaviour of the inhabitants of Constantí shows that not everywhere in Spain women were more committed to religious practice than men. If there existed a notion of the feminisation of religion in

this region, it is impossible it was based on observation and was necessarily imported. The same would be true for another Tarragona municipality, Bisbal de Falset, where 400 men and 300 women of a population slightly over 800 communed in 1912.³⁴ As for the men of Constantí, their electoral behaviour did not tend towards the Catholic and conservative parties; in the period analysed here, they voted, in great part, for liberal monarchist forces³⁵. While Constantí was mostly rural at the end of the nineteenth century, its inhabitants were well informed about the happenings in the rest of Catalonia and in Spain, in general, as the municipality is found right between Reus and Tarragona, the two major towns of the Tarragona province, and many people passed through it when travelling to one of the two towns.

Despite its earlier different pattern, the municipality of Constantí ended up following the same trend as Alforja, Rourell and Rauric: by 1932, with its population surpassing 2000, the situation had changed radically. Three times more men than women failed to fulfil their Holy Week duty. While the number of female abstainers (110) stayed was the same as in 1901, 360 men abstained in 1932 (Duch, 2016, p. 279). This shows that in Constantí it was during the first third of the twentieth century, not before, when men and women of the municipality began to adapt their religious behaviour to the patterns that were hegemonic in Spain as a whole.

The region of Tarragona is an example of a variety of patterns, trends, and timings³⁶. Overall, we can appreciate that there was a change in the religious behaviour of Spanish men and women in the first decades of the twen-

³² *Boletín Oficial de la provincia de Tarragona*, 8 April 1893, p. 2; *Diario de Reus*, 21 May 1901, p. 2; *El Tarraconense*, 16 April 1916, p. 1.

³³ AHAT, 7.48.1.2.5.1. Constantí. Parròquia de Sant Felíu.

³⁴ *Cartas edificantes de la provincia de Aragón. Año 1912*. Manresa, Imprenta y encuadernación de San José, 1913, p. 12.

³⁵ *Boletín Oficial de la provincia de Tarragona*, 8 April 1893, p. 2; *Diario de Reus*, 21 May 1901, p. 2.

³⁶ Different patterns, trends, and timings can be found in the Diocese of Segovia during the Second Republic: Marcos del Olmo (2022, p. 130-138).

TABLE 7. Number of men and women who did not fulfill their Easter duties in Constantí.

Year	Men	Women
1893	6	9
1894	8	11
1895	12	27
1896	12	32
1897	13	38
1898	13	52
1899	15	68
1900	19	75
1901	23	94

Source: Constantí. Parròquia de Sant Feliu, 7.48, AHAT.

tieth century, while the ideas that linked religiousness to femininity had circulated in Spain for many decades. These findings invite the historians to endorse the hypothesis that in some regions of Spain, the greater commitment of women to religious practice was a consequence, not a cause of the assimilation of the ideas concerning the discursive feminisation of religion that had penetrated social imaginary and political vocabulary at least since the second half of the nineteenth century. This hypothesis can be also applied when analysing the decreasing participation of men in pious activities, because the notion of religion as an inherent feature of women was linked, above all, with confession and attending masses. In other words, the men of Tarragona distanced themselves from everyday religious activities, particularly from the ordinary ones carried out in everyday life, when these suffered a drop in prestige due to their association with femininity and the men endorsed such understanding.

Nonetheless, Catholic men continued to display their commitment to the Church in the first decades of the twentieth century, albeit in a different way. The case of Tarragona also proves that. Men acted collectively in defence of Catholicism, attended in great number the events that were advertised as for men only and kept participating in a number similar to that of women on special religious occasions, such as general communes during the Holy Week.³⁷ Men did not cease to participate in the most prestigious and socially-visible religious practices and they also actively engaged when there was a possibility to wield power and act as leaders within the Catholic lay movement. At the turn of the century, the men of Tarragona who considered themselves Catholics were ready to give up the fulfilment of ordinary religious duties, as they

³⁷ *La Cruz*, 1 January 1907, p. 1; *La Cruz*, 24 February 1910, p. 1; *La Cruz*, 15 July 1926, p. 2; *La Cruz*, 29 February 1928, p. 2; *La Cruz*, 15 April 1930, p. 1; *La Cruz*, 27 June 1930, p. 3.

considered it as something feminine, but this attitude did not prevent them from engaging with the Catholic religion and Church in private and in public. Not only did they prove their commitment in new prestigious spaces of sociability such as the press, political parties, or professional associations, but they attended massively when took place a public event that they considered as suitable for their public display of religiousness³⁸.

In these regions, the strategy of re-masculinisation of religion at the turn of the century, rather than to bring men back to Catholicism, strove to prevent the believers from being influenced by secular discourses that, in a fight for hegemony, presented religious practice as hard to combine with true manhood. As in these areas, the great part of men fulfilled their religious duties, the mission consisted not of bringing indifferent or hostile men back to the flock, but rather of fighting in the discursive field to prevent the faithful from abandoning pious practices. Thus, for instance, when remarking on the success in terms of men's massive participation in the 1910 Corpus Christi procession in Tarragona, a Catholic commentator argued that these public displays of devotion by men were essential for the committed Catholics to get "respect among the unbelievers [*descreídos*]. If we retire, they will get braver [in demanding that] we do not demonstrate publicly our faith and then [in trying] to deny us the rights of Catholic citizens."³⁹

The fact that men in Tarragona displayed greater commitment to religious practice than in many other regions of Spain, surely contributed to the optimism that is observable in the local Catholic journal *La Cruz* concerning the engagement of men with Catholicism, an optimistic attitude that is striking when compared to the Catholic press in many other Spanish and European regions. In my opinion, this explains the optimistic statements -unsupported by statistics- about the increasing commitment of men to religious duties in Madrid, France, Belgium, Germany, or the Netherlands, supposedly because such practices were not considered sanctimonious and prudish "anymore."⁴⁰ Even when the articles in *La Cruz* focused on religiosity in France, they differed from the above-mentioned articles that complained about the extremely low numbers of Parisians who fulfilled their religious duties. *La Cruz* was more optimistic and provided data that supported the idea that French men appeared in higher numbers than women at public events in defence of Catholic interests.⁴¹

CONCLUSIONS

Spanish historiography showed little interest in applying a gender perspective to religious history until the late 1990s. Once the first studies on the feminisation of religion in Spain appeared, though, they followed the most

³⁸ Similar things have been proved, with their own particularities, in Germany: Doney (2022).

³⁹ *La Cruz*, 22 May 1910, p. 2.

⁴⁰ *La Cruz*, 30 March 1924, p. 1.

⁴¹ *La Cruz*, 25 October 1924, 1; *La Cruz*, 20 January 1925, p. 1.

recent trends in international historiography. They strove to provide a cultural and discursive analysis of the phenomenon, leaving aside the analysis of the data on the religious practice of the Spanish men and women. In this article I have taken the unexplored path, analysing the data to contribute to the debate on the religious commitment of women and men in Spain, in a dialogue with these cultural and discursive analyses. In my opinion, analysing the data on the fulfilment of religious duties helps us nuance and enrich the discursive analyses of the feminisation and re-masculinisation of religion.

Adding a quantitative study to purely discursive analyses can prevent unjustified generalisations and clears the way for the articulation of new hypotheses on this issue. The analysis of the numbers makes it possible to explore the “reality” of religious practices in each region and contrast it to the perceptions the contemporaries had concerning the religiosity of men and women. Moreover, it allows a nuanced analysis of the strategies and intensity of the projects aimed at re-masculinising the religion in one place or another. The challenge Catholic elites and activists faced when articulating and disseminating their ideas about Catholic men’s virility obviously varied greatly in different regions of the country. During the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, for instance, the assimilation of the discourse on the feminisation of religion might have not been so straightforward in regions when the fulfilment of Holy Week duties was overwhelming for both sexes, and the people could not confirm such notion by direct observation. This would be the case of Sena, Vadillo, Albiol, Almo-ster, Guialmons, Creixell, Vespella de Gaià or the Diocese of Zamora. In other areas, such as the municipalities in the Tarragona province like Alforja, Rourell or Rauric, people could indeed appreciate a major difference in the fulfilment of Holy Week duties by men when compared to women. The specific examples given throughout the article show a great variety of situations, as well as different trends in each dynamic, even in relatively homogeneous regions, such as the parishes of the Madrid city centre.

The data I have outlined (even though it is a very limited sample) provide us with a starting point from which to ponder on the conundrum of whether the greater participation of women in religious duties in some locations led to the creation of the notion of female religiosity or, whether it was the discursive link of women with religion that stimulated their greater participation and drove many men away from everyday religious practice. If the latter is true, then, when the notion that women were more religious than men became hegemonic, many women felt the need to show their religiousness in public daily.

While men may have distanced themselves from ordinary pious practices, this did not necessarily mean they distanced themselves from the religion and the Catholic Church. Many men considered everyday religious practices as incompatible with masculinity, but they deemed it appropriate to display religious commitment sporadically, particularly on special occasions. In fact, the data prove that men frequently participated in similar numbers as women when the mass or the commune took place on

special occasions (important holidays or specific exceptional events). This new empirical evidence sheds light on this phenomenon, opening new horizons in the interpretation of the ways Spanish men conceptualised religion in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century. The interpretations that stress Catholic men’s indifference towards religious practices should be nuanced and take into consideration the existence of other spaces and ways of engagement as active Catholics, not only in the new, masculinised spaces of sociability such as politics or press, but also in specifically Catholic events, particularly the extraordinary and more visible ones.

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